

Survey of university students - Evaluation of teaching : an integrated approach to promoting a quality culture

Enquête auprès des étudiants universitaires - L'évaluation de l'enseignement : une approche intégrée pour la promotion de la culture qualité

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Abstract

The article points out that the assessment of teachers by students is of crucial importance and fully aligns with the process of continuous improvement in education. It aims to obtain valuable feedback from students to identify strengths to be emphasized and weaknesses to be addressed in our teaching. This approach allows us to make necessary corrections, evolve our pedagogical practices, and ensure a quality learning experience.

By paying particular attention to the engagement of learners in expressing their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the content and pedagogical methods offered to them, we enhance the credibility and validity of any pedagogical reform. Students thus become active participants in their own education, and their voice becomes an essential component for evaluating the effectiveness of our teachers and the education system as a whole.

The survey carried out among students at Hassan II University reveals general dissatisfaction with what the university has to offer, the equipment available, the teaching methods adopted, the quality of training and the performance of human resources. These results underline the importance of systematically incorporating student feedback into improvement processes.

Keywords: Evaluation of teaching; Quality culture; Strengths and weaknesses of the education system; Assessment of teachers by students.

Résumé

L'article souligne que l'appréciation des enseignants par les étudiants revêt une importance cruciale et s'inscrit pleinement dans le processus d'amélioration continue de la formation. Elle vise à obtenir une rétroaction précieuse auprès des étudiants afin d'identifier les points forts à valoriser et les points faibles à améliorer dans notre enseignement. Cette démarche nous permet d'apporter les corrections nécessaires, de faire évoluer nos pratiques pédagogiques et de garantir une expérience d'apprentissage de qualité.

En accordant une attention particulière à l'engagement des apprenants dans l'expression de leur satisfaction ou de leur insatisfaction vis-à-vis des contenus et des méthodes pédagogiques qui leur sont proposés, nous renforçons la crédibilité et la validité de toute réforme pédagogique. Les étudiants deviennent ainsi des acteurs actifs de leur propre éducation, et leur voix devient une composante essentielle pour évaluer l'efficacité de nos enseignants et du système éducatif dans son ensemble.

L'enquête menée auprès des étudiants de l'université Hassan II révèle une insatisfaction générale concernant les offres du milieu universitaire, le matériel existant, les méthodes pédagogiques adoptées, la qualité des formations et les prestations des ressources humaines. Ces résultats soulignent l'importance d'intégrer systématiquement le feedback des étudiants dans les processus d'amélioration.

Mots clés : Evaluation de l'enseignement ; Culture qualité ; Amélioration continue de la formation ; Appréciation des enseignants par les étudiants.

Introduction

Educational evaluation plays a fundamental role in the development and improvement of education systems throughout the world. In a context where the quality of education has become a major concern, it is essential to understand how evaluation can be used as an effective tool to promote a culture of quality in educational institutions. This article provides an in-depth exploration of the relationship between educational evaluation and quality culture, highlighting the synergies and challenges inherent in this dynamic. (Hadji, 1995).

Quality culture, defined as a set of shared values, norms and behaviours aimed at achieving excellence, has become a priority for many educational institutions. The recognition of the importance of quality culture in higher education and other levels of education is the result of a collective awareness of the need to continuously improve the quality of teaching and learning. (Kellghan & Greaney, 2002).

Educational evaluation can be seen as a key process for cultivating a culture of quality in educational institutions. It provides valuable information about the strengths and weaknesses of the education system, identifies areas for improvement and enables informed decisions to be made to enhance the quality of teaching. By integrating the evaluation of teaching into an overall approach to quality culture, educational establishments can create an environment conducive to continuous improvement, pedagogical innovation and student success. (Hénard & Roseveare, 2012)

However, establishing a harmonious relationship between educational evaluation and quality culture is not without its challenges. Issues related to objectivity, validity of measurements, stakeholder participation and implementation of recommendations can be obstacles to overcome. However, by developing rigorous evaluation approaches, promoting transparency and accountability, and encouraging collaboration between education stakeholders, it is possible to overcome these challenges and create a culture where educational evaluation is seen as a driver for continuous improvement.

In this article, we will examine the different dimensions of educational evaluation and its link with quality culture. We will discuss existing evaluation models, the tools and methodologies used to evaluate teaching, and good practices for effectively integrating evaluation into a quality culture. By exploring the relationship between educational evaluation and quality culture, this

article aims to provide valuable insights for policy makers, educational practitioners and researchers interested in improving the quality of education. (De Ketele, 2014).

We propose a review of the literature by citing the significant works which are in line with our object of study. In the field of the evaluation of teaching and quality culture, the work of Harvey and Green (1993) laid the conceptual foundations of quality in higher education, emphasising the importance of a holistic approach. They highlighted the fact that quality is not limited to quantitative indicators, but also encompasses qualitative aspects linked to the learning experience. Following on from these ideas, developed the concept of constructive alignment, which emphasises the coherence between learning objectives, teaching methods and assessments. This approach fits in perfectly with an integrated quality culture.

Student evaluation of teaching (SOT) is a central aspect of this approach. Marsh (2007) has conducted extensive research into SRE, demonstrating its validity and reliability when properly implemented. His work highlights the importance of CBE as a tool for continuous improvement in teaching. Furthermore, explored the factors influencing the effectiveness of IEE, highlighting the importance of training teachers in the interpretation and use of assessment results. These elements are particularly relevant to our hypothesis on the integration of EEE results into curriculum revision.

Student engagement also plays a crucial role in this dynamic. have studied the impact of active student participation on the quality of higher education, showing that their involvement in evaluation and improvement processes contributes significantly to the overall quality of the educational experience. With regard to programme review and continuous improvement, the research of has highlighted the importance of a systemic and collaborative approach. They emphasise the need to integrate student feedback into this process, which echoes our problematic on the articulation between MEE and the periodic review of programmes. Lattuca and Stark (2009)

Quality culture in higher education is also an important topic. has explored this concept, highlighting the involvement of all stakeholders, including students. Finally, it is essential to consider the challenges and prospects of educational evaluation. Benton and Cashin (2012) have examined the challenges of using EEE, including issues of bias and interpretation of results. Their research offers avenues for improving the validity and usefulness of EEE, which is relevant to ensuring the rigour and validity of results.

This literature review highlights the wealth of existing research on teaching evaluation, quality culture and student engagement. It also highlights the relevance of our approach, which integrates the EEE into a broader process of continuous improvement and programme review. Our research hypotheses are in line with this work, while providing a new perspective on the relationship between EEE and quality culture in the specific context of Hassan II University.

If the education and training system is to be part of a culture of quality, it must submit to two binding requirements : continuous assessment and periodic revision of curricula. In this context, the evaluation of teaching by students (EEE) is emerging as an essential tool for measuring the quality of teaching. However, it is necessary to resolve the problem of effectively integrating SRE while respecting the requirements of continuous assessment and periodic programme review. How can a system of CBE be put in place that allows students to provide constructive feedback on teaching on a regular basis ? How can this information be used to improve teaching on an ongoing basis and to guide the revision of programmes in a relevant way ? This issue calls for in-depth consideration of the methods used in EEE, their relationship with other forms of evaluation, and the mechanisms for effectively using the results of EEE to promote a culture of quality in the education and training system.

Regular incorporation of the results of student evaluation of teaching into the curriculum review process enables continuous and proactive adaptation of the curriculum, taking into account the needs and expectations of learners, leading to an overall improvement in the quality of teaching.

The establishment of transparent, two-way communication between students, teachers and decision-makers promotes the effective use of the results of the evaluation of teaching by students, encouraging dialogue, the exchange of ideas and collaborative decision-making to promote a culture of quality in the education and training system.

Relevance of research : Research into the impact of student evaluation of teaching (SEE) on improving the education and training system is highly relevant and of scientific value. Here are a few reasons why this topic is useful and relevant :

- Improving the quality of education : EEE offers a unique and direct perspective on students' experience and perception of teaching. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses perceived by students, educators and policy makers can make the necessary adjustments to improve the quality of teaching, focusing on the needs of learners. (Marsh, & Roche, 1997)

- Student engagement and satisfaction : EEE allows students to feel heard and involved in the process of improving teaching. By giving students a voice and valuing their feedback, it fosters their engagement, satisfaction and motivation, which can have a positive impact on their learning and performance. (Kuh, & Hu, 2001)

- Adapting curricula to the needs of learners : By regularly incorporating the results of the EEE into the revision of curricula, educational establishments can ensure that programmes meet the current needs of learners. This ensures the relevance and quality of the content taught, taking into account changes in society, new technologies and educational trends. (Stark, & Lattuca, 1997).

- Informed decision-making : The EEA provides valuable data and information that can be used as a basis for informed decision-making. The results of the EEE can help decision-makers identify priority areas for improvement, allocate resources effectively and implement targeted initiatives to enhance the quality of education. (Harvey, 2004).

- Culture of quality in education : By focusing on the EEE, educational institutions can promote a culture of quality where evaluation and improvement of teaching become integrated and continuous practices. This fosters a mindset of continuous improvement, pedagogical innovation and teacher professional development. (Bénard, & Dufour, 2015).

1. Methodology

1.1. Objectives:

- To gather the views of trainees on the relevance of their initial training.
- To measure the quality perceived by students of the university training on offer.

In this context, the contribution of the quality approach is crucial. A good quality university training offer is one that starts from the qualities required of the job in order to formalise the output of the training course, whereas the input is based on an analysis of the needs of the future beneficiaries of the training. From this idea stems the concern to measure the satisfaction rate of training beneficiaries and to address students to find out how they perceive their training programmes and also their opinions on the performance of their teachers. For this reason, we opted to initiate an evaluation in the form of a survey of students who receive training within the curricula of Hassan II University.

Our aim in carrying out this study is to gather answers to questions addressed to university students, such as the following :

Are the students who are the focus of the reform satisfied with the teaching they receive ?

What attitudes and reactions do they have to this change in structures and methods ?

1.2. The approach adopted

We targeted the population of university students continuing their education in one of the courses of study at Hassan II University who gave us an assessment of the quality of the training services. To do this, we adopted a quantitative approach based on a questionnaire survey,

1.3. Purpose of the questionnaire:

The aim of this questionnaire is to sound out the main stakeholders for whom the reform project is intended.

This type of survey aims to obtain quantifiable statistical data on a specific population. To do this, the questionnaire is administered to a representative sample of the target population, i.e. to a group of sufficient size, in terms of number of individuals, for the answers given to be representative of the overall opinion of this population.

The aim of our survey is to analyse the trends of the respondents using figures and quantitative methods. We will be using statistical tools to describe and understand phenomena. (Field, 2018).

Students are already seen as internal customers of the modern entrepreneurial university. This is the target population we asked to respond to our survey. Their opinions are very important to us because they are in the best position to give us credible information. Managers, for their part, are now well aware that the success of higher education depends to a large extent on the satisfaction of the students who receive the training and also on the satisfaction of the teaching staff who are responsible for delivering the training. (Kuh, & Whitt, 1988).

1.4. Measurement scales and psychometrics

When we want to carry out a study to address an issue, we have several options open to us: we can conduct a qualitative study to gather qualitative information and gain a better understanding of the facts, or we can choose to carry out a quantitative study if we want to obtain quantitative

results. In our case, we opted for measurement scales, which are very useful in a quantitative analysis because they allow us to quantify the data. (DeVellis, 2016).

We opted for a measurement scale known as the Likert scale, which belongs to the category of ordinal scales. This scale is very popular and is often used in scientific surveys. It allows for nuances in respondents' answers and also for different degrees of judgement in the analysis of results. (Joshi, et al., 2015).

1.5. Measurement scale : Likert scale

To formalise our measurement scale enabling us to quantify the satisfaction rate of training beneficiaries, our first choice was to use a universally recognised theoretical model. We borrowed the 5M model known as the Ishikawa diagram. (Ishikawa, 1986).

The 5M method (Environment, Material, Method, Manpower, Raw Material) consists of reviewing the families of factors that explain a phenomenon.

1.5.1. Définition

The 5M method or Ishikawa diagram, cause-effect diagram, is a tool for identifying the causes leading to an effect. It is an analytical approach which consists of going back to the essential causes of the problem.

Parameter	Description
<u>Environment</u>	Infrastructure, space, noise, lighting, risk prevention, etc.
<u>Materials</u>	Raw materials, documents, data, information, traceability, etc.
<u>Methods</u>	Work rules, procedures, protocols, reliability of results,
<u>Labour</u>	Qualification, training, motivation, definition of tasks, etc.
<u>Equipment</u>	Machine, tools, maintenance, capacity, etc.

The 5 M's according to the Ishikawa diagram

1.5.2 The Ishikawa model adapted to our object of study is :

Dimension	Description of items
Environment	School infrastructure and equipment ; administration and its premises the department's intake structure and capacity ; the spaces for theoretical and practical courses ; the spaces reserved for micro-teaching, etc.
Materials	Teaching and learning materials ; Technical and scientific aids ; Electronic and digital material resources ; Audiovisual material resources ; etc.
Methods	Teaching methods ; Learning strategies ; Didactic and pedagogical approaches and pedagogical approaches ; Supervision and assessment methods ; Incentives and motivation ; Communication channels ; The relational aspect and the teaching climate; ...
Manpower	Teacher competence ; Governance of the administration ; Leadership of the headteacher ; Expertise of the placement tutors ; Expertise of the heads of the various sectors ; etc.
Subjects	Quality of the training on offer ; Visibility of the training pathway ; Clarity and of the modules ; Relevance of the objectives and target skills ; Quality of the work placement of the training course ; Attractiveness and employability of the sector ; Digitalisation of training ; Professionalisation of training ; etc.

Dimensions and their corresponding items

Therefore, our measuring instrument that we constructed to be able to gauge the satisfaction rate of training beneficiaries is composed of 5 dimensions and 30 items addressed to a sample of students pursuing their studies at Hassan University.

1.6. Metric qualities of our measurement instruments (Practical framework)

<u>Summary of comments processed</u>			
		<u>N</u>	<u>%</u>
<u>Observations</u>	<u>Valide</u>	<u>378</u>	<u>100</u>
	<u>Exclus^a</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>
	<u>Total</u>	<u>378</u>	<u>100</u>
a. <u>Suppression par liste basée sur toutes les variables de la procédure.</u>			

<u>Reliability statistics</u>		
Alpha de Cronbach	Alpha de Cronbach basé sur des éléments normalisés	Nombre d'éléments
0,960	0,960	30

Educational evaluation plays a fundamental role in the development and improvement of education systems throughout the world. In a context where the quality of education has become a major concern, it is essential to understand how evaluation can be used as an effective tool to promote a culture of quality in educational institutions. This article provides an in-depth exploration of the relationship between teacher evaluation and quality culture, highlighting the synergies and challenges inherent in this dynamic.

2. Results and data analysis

2.1 Environment : Analysis and data

Environment		
Do you feel you take every opportunity offered by your training environment ?		
Item	Dissatisfaction rate (DR)	Satisfaction rate (SR)
Item 1 : The school's infrastructure and equipment	75%	25%
Item 2 : The school's administration, premises and facilities	69%	31%

Item 3 : The department's intake structure and capacity	68%	32%
Item 4 : Theoretical and practical course areas	67%	33%
Item 5 : Spaces reserved for micro-teaching	67%	33%
Item 6 : Spaces for extracurricular activities	65%	35%

Student satisfaction rate for each item in the Environment dimension

Environment					
Do you feel you take every opportunity offered by your training environment ?					
	Response	Score	Proportion	DR	SR
Environment	Very dissatisfied	330	15%	68%	32%
	Dissatisfied	645	28%		
	Less satisfied	577	25%		
	Notvery satisfied	379	17%		
	Satisfied	280	12%		
	Very satisfied	57	3%		
	TOTAL	2268	100%		

The satisfaction rate of students in the entire "Environment" dimension

Perceived quality of the environment

75% dissatisfaction with the extracurricular spaces reserved for out-of-class activities : A university's educational performance cannot be improved solely in classrooms reserved for

teaching formal programmes. It can also be improved by self-development and self-training activities in other spaces such as the library, audiovisual rooms, etc.

World-class universities pay particular attention to these areas. It relies heavily on the development activities that take place in these areas to help students acquire cross-disciplinary skills and softskills.

69% dissatisfied with infrastructure and equipment : Infrastructure and equipment are one of the key factors in the success of a training project. A lack of infrastructure and equipment could certainly weaken the chances of success of any project, and could also be detrimental to achieving the expected results. Indeed, the wealth or precariousness of the institute in terms of infrastructure and equipment is a source of failure or success of the educational reform. The institute's performance in terms of acquiring teaching and professional skills also depends on its investment in this area.

The infrastructure and equipment variable is one of the key factors in initiating a project and ensuring its feasibility and effectiveness. A clear definition of the project's objectives is not enough to implement it; putting effective resources in place is also crucial. Very often, actions are taken to achieve what has been planned, ignoring the infrastructure variable. The result is obviously perceptible, either an abortion halfway through the project, or a poorly calculated outcome and a disappointing end.

68% dissatisfied with the spaces for theoretical and practical courses : A large proportion of university students' time is spent in theory and practical classrooms ; whether these areas are managed well or badly would undoubtedly have a positive or negative impact on the quality of the university education on offer. An attractive space for learners is one that does not pollute, allowing them to concentrate more fully on their lessons and providing them with clear vision and well-filtered hearing, free from all noise interference.

Classrooms are the ideal place to acquire skills, and the richness of these spaces can only be beneficial to learners. Equipping these rooms with scientific and electronic tools would undoubtedly produce satisfactory results for those receiving training. (Gonzalez, & Wagenaar, 2003).

67% dissatisfied with the department's facilities and supply capacity : The department is the space par excellence where the teaching/learning process takes place. Its structure and capacity strongly influence the pedagogical atmosphere of the course; it is the department that generates

discomfort or ease in the course. Students expect a great deal from the department, which is responsible for building their identity through its unique offerings. It acts as a mediator between the precursors of the offer and the beneficiaries of the training.

The department's intake structure and supply capacity clearly reflect its performance in terms of the quality of its goods and services. (Tardif, & Lessard, 2011).

67% dissatisfied with micro-teaching facilities : The importance attached to micro-teaching spaces is a concrete expression of the training paradigm adopted by the educational players. The use of micro-teaching provides information about the particular attention paid to reflexivity and knowing how to act.

Students very often express their satisfaction whenever they see that their institute has good structures for practical work and tutorials, guaranteeing the weaving together of theoretical and scientific foundations and their practical applications.

Teacher training colleges give a great deal of importance to micro-teaching; it is thanks to this capital that the older generations have been able to benefit from consistent, good quality training.

65% dissatisfied with the administration and its premises) : The dissatisfaction of training beneficiaries with the administration and its premises reflects their dissatisfaction with the spaces offering administrative services. This may be due to its architectural design, which reflects classic, traditional leadership.

The administration building symbolically represents the top of the hierarchy, and by its structure and proximity, the student can easily deduce the premises of the administrative management adopted. They will undoubtedly understand whether their leader's style is welcoming and benevolent or rather directive and bureaucratic.

The institution's brand image is built up from the moment students are welcomed until they complete their course. The administration is the key element responsible for embellishing its training courses through its logistical and management actions. (Kuh, & Whitt, 1988).

2.2. Material : Data analysis

Hardware		
Are you really making the most of the hardware resources available ?		
Item	DR	SR
Item 7 : Are you satisfied with the effective use of teaching and learning materials ?	68%	32%
Item 8 : Are you satisfied with the use of technical and scientific aids ?	69%	31%
Item 9 : Are you satisfied with the use of electronic and digital resources ?	70%	30%
Item 10 : Are you satisfied with the use of audiovisual material resources ?	70%	30%

Student satisfaction rate for each item in the "Equipment" dimension

Hardware					
Are you really making the most of the hardware resources available ?					
Hardware	Response	Score	Proportion	DR	SR
	Very dissatisfied	221	14%	69%	31%
	Dissatisfied	382	25%		
	Less satisfied	458	30%		
	Notvery satisfied	280	18%		
	Satisfied	154	10%		
	Very satisfied	32	2%		
	TOTAL	1527	100%		

The satisfaction rate of students across the entire "Equipment" dimension

Perceived quality of equipment

70% dissatisfied with the material resources available (Electronic and digital material resources) : Today, any training course that does not have electronic and digital equipment is considered to be outdated and outmoded. Updating the spirit of training and exploiting digital culture has become a priority. It is this indicator that enables us to distinguish between a traditional university offering and a modern one. Today, encouraging students to get more involved in their work has become possible through inverted pedagogy, which adopts the use of digital tools. Students are becoming very involved through digital culture. (Karsenti, & Collin, 2013).

70% dissatisfied with the material resources available (Audiovisual material resources) : The presence of up-to-date material and audiovisual resources will enable universities to diversify their educational offerings. This can help universities to solve a number of problems, such as massification, remedial courses and distance learning. In addition, certain specialities that are difficult to teach in certain regions due to a lack of resources can be taught via video-conferencing, without the need for experts in the field to travel.

The benefits of audiovisual material resources are enormous, some of which are listed below :

- Improving the intake structure and supply capacity of the university and its departments.
- Improving the amount of time students spend engaged in their learning.
- diversifying teaching styles and adopting new, more relevant approaches
- Introducing new techniques and methods
- Introducing a new approach to teaching

69% dissatisfied with the material resources available (Technical and scientific aids) : Technical and scientific aids play a very important role in clarifying processes; they help the teacher to make abstract concepts operational and conversely they help to underpin practical illustrations with learned doctrines. The teacher relies heavily on technical and scientific aids in his didactic transposition to make excessively formalised programmed knowledge accessible to his students. While scientific support has a certain nobility, technical support also has its share of contribution to make. . (Tardif, 2006).

68% dissatisfied with the material resources available (teaching and learning materials) : The conceptualisation of a training project quite often begins with preliminary studies that take place before the training content is designed and planned. Studying the context and analysing the needs of the trainees is a crucial stage that should not be rushed. Identifying requirements and resources is also vital.

Material resources, in particular teaching and learning materials, are a key factor in the success of training provision. A shortage or lack of teaching and learning materials is a source of discomfort for both the training provider and the trainees. An effective teacher is one who prepares the ground better so that his students can get the most out of his teaching; he is a teacher who clearly defines the direction and the appropriate means to get there. These means include teaching and learning materials, i.e. any instrument that helps to achieve the general objectives of the course. These tools are closely linked to the specific nature of the subject. In short, synergy between ends and means is crucial. (Gagné, & Driscoll, 2005).

2.3. Method : Data analysis

Method		
Do you think the methods adopted by your institution are relevant and effective ?		
Item	DR	SR
Item 11 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of teaching methods ?	62%	38%
Item 12 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of learning strategies ?	64%	36%

Item 13 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of teaching and learning approaches ?	64%	36%
Item 14 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of supervision and evaluation arrangements ?	65%	35%
Item 15 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of incentive and motivation measures ?	65%	35%
Item 16 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of communication channels ?	66%	34%
Item 17 : Are you satisfied with the relevance and effectiveness of the relational aspect and the teaching climate ?	64%	36%

Student satisfaction rate for each item in the "Method" dimension

Method					
Do you think the methods adopted by your institution are relevant and effective ?					
	Response	Score	Proportion	DR	SR
Method	Very dissatisfied	293	11%	64%	36%
	Dissatisfied	663	25%		
	Less satisfied	749	28%		
	Notvery satisfied	512	19%		
	Satisfied	339	13%		
	Very satisfied	90	3%		
	TOTAL	2646	100%		

Student satisfaction rate for the entire "Method" dimension

Perceived quality of Method

- The survey results reveal a high level of dissatisfaction (64%) with the institution's communication methods, compared with only 36% satisfaction. This significant disparity points to a major problem in the current communications strategy. The channels used seem ill-adapted to the needs and preferences of modern students, potentially resulting in gaps in the transmission of crucial information. This can lead to a disconnect between the institution and its student community, negatively impacting the overall academic experience. An urgent review of communication practices is needed, requiring a thorough analysis of student needs and the adoption of more effective and interactive channels to significantly improve student satisfaction and engagement.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (incentive and motivation approaches): Encouraging learners is one of the requirements, and their involvement is a source of success in the learning process. The teacher's investment in this area is crucial. Starting from the learner's motives for action provides a favourable teaching climate and a high degree of assurance that the expected results will be achieved. Training beneficiaries can only be satisfied if their needs are met.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (supervision and assessment methods): Student supervision and assessment is an essential stage in the teaching/learning process. This action of checking what has been learnt has been recommended by objective-based teaching to ensure that teaching is being carried out properly. The underlying reasons for assessment are to check whether the teaching given to students has been effective, whether the approaches adopted by the teacher have been relevant and rigorous, and whether the training content has been coherent and consistent.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (the relational aspect and the teaching climate): A teacher's teaching style has a major influence on the quality of his or her teaching. The nature of the teaching climate they offer their students and the relational aspect they use to get their learners to learn is a source of inspiration or concern for their students. A teacher who adopts a participatory approach will have a lot of luck getting his students to interact and be cooperative in solving the problems raised by him and by the programmes. (Weimer, 2013).

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (didactic and pedagogical approaches): Today, these models have shown their inadequacies and are beginning to become the subject of a number of criticisms because of their limiting factors. The arguments are many and varied, but here are the most important ones. These models are obsolete and reductive, and do not focus on the learner and his or her motives for action. These models are notorious for being too theoretical, too lecture-based in relation to the needs and realities of the field, and for the passive nature of student learning. The assessment of students is most often based solely on their ability to memorise, and the transmission of information is favoured over the process of integrating and building skills. The high-level skills required remain difficult to acquire and develop. (Perrenoud, 1999).

The world of education is beginning to draw inspiration from these schools by transposing their models, which are considered to be humanist and constructivist, and new, supposedly promising, models have emerged, bringing with them a fresh look at the problems posed.

The concept of learning has been redefined by cognitivists and constructivists, with other promising attributes.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (Learning strategies)

For many years, there has been talk of improving the quality of higher education. Today, the challenge for every university is to make the transition from a quantitative perspective, based on student flows, to a more qualitative one.

The proposed reform of university curricula proposes a modular teaching model, the cross-cutting objective of which is to enable students to acquire an academic culture but also to help them build the skills they need to move forward in the professional world. (Biggs, & Tang 2011).

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (Teaching methods): A training project is a set of objectives and the means to achieve them. The choice of objectives determines the direction to be taken, and the means are the actions to be taken to achieve them. In teaching, the methods aim to take shortcuts to get to the target early. In vocational training, the ultimate aim is to prepare the trainee for the job, and the relevant methods are those that enable students to acquire the qualities required for the job. It is therefore active teaching based on the construction of resources and their development that ensures the relevance and effectiveness of the training offered. (Kolb, 2014). Alternation is an effective way of weaving together learned doctrines and practical applications.

2.4. Labour : Data analysis

Labour		
Are you satisfied with the performance of your institution's human resources ?		
Item	DR	SR
Item 18 : Competence of teachers	49%	51%
Item 19 : Governance of the administration	63%	37%
Item 20 : Leadership of the headteacher].	59%	41%
Item 21 : Expertise of placement tutors]	61%	39%
Item 22 : Expertise of sector managers	54%	46%

Student satisfaction rate for each item in the "Labour" dimension

Labour					
Are you satisfied with the performance of your institution's human resources ?					
Labour	Response	Score	Proportion	DR	SR
	Very dissatisfied	181	10%	56%	44%
	Dissatisfied	441	24%		
	Less satisfied	412	22%		

	Notvery satisfied	299	16%		
	Satisfied	366	20%		
	Very satisfied	143	8%		
	TOTAL	1842	100%		

The satisfaction rate of students in the entire "Labour" dimension

Perceived quality of Labour

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (Governance of administrative staff): The performance expected of teaching staff is obvious, particularly in terms of engineering and teaching scenarios, whereas what is expected of administrative staff is much more focused on governance and human resources management.

Competent administrative staff are staff who also give satisfaction to students, who are considered to be the institution's internal customers. The quality of the welcome, the responsiveness of the response to their requests, the dissemination and communication of reliable information, good management of the training facilities, etc. are the skills claimed by the beneficiaries of training.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (Expertise of placement tutors): The placement tutor is the person entrusted with the students' professional awareness and integration. They have a very important role to play, as they are responsible for familiarising students with their future workplace, supporting them in professional situations, listening to them and answering their questions and concerns, helping them to acquire genuine professional

skills and building their portfolio of skills with them. In short, to work with them in situations of alternation and reflexivity.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (Headteacher leadership): The headteacher is the person most called upon to promote all the training courses accredited by the higher authorities. No training offer, however well put together, can guarantee the quality of the services provided. The head of the school is the conductor of the orchestra and is the focus of all quality management actions. He or she must demonstrate strong managerial leadership. They face a wide range of challenges, including motivating their teams (administrative staff and teaching staff), empowering their employees and getting them on board with their projects, managing conflicts and unforeseen events, and encouraging their students to make an effort and get involved in personal and professional projects.

- Dissatisfaction with the methods adopted by the institution (Expertise of heads of programmes): The head of course is directly responsible for the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the teaching staff responsible for supervising and supporting students. He or she is also directly responsible for the perceived quality of the training received by the students. He is the person responsible for the success or failure of a university training programme. In fact, the formalization of a training programme and the day-to-day management of the training. They must demonstrate perfect mastery of three types of leadership : academic leadership, managerial leadership and relational leadership.

2.5. Raw material : Data analysis

RAW MATERIALS		
Are you satisfied overall with your training course ?		
Item	DR	SR
Item 23 : Are you satisfied overall with the Quality of the training on offer ?	63%	37%
Item 24 : Are you satisfied overall with the Visibility of your training path ?	66%	34%
Item 25 : Are you satisfied overall with the clarity and layout of the modules ?	65%	35%

Item 26 : Are you satisfied with the relevance of the objectives and skills targeted ?	65%	35%
Item 27 : Are you satisfied with the quality of the training course ?	62%	38%
Item 28 : Are you satisfied with the attractiveness and employability of the sector ?	61%	39%
Item 29 : Are you satisfied with the digitisation of training ?	66%	34%
Item 30 : Are you satisfied with the professionalism of your training ?	62%	38%

Student satisfaction rate for each item in the "Raw materials" dimension

RAW MATERIALS					
Are you satisfied overall with your training course ?					
	Response	Score	Proportion	DR	SR
RAW MATERIALS	Very dissatisfied	378	13%	65%	35%
	Dissatisfied	727	25%		
	Less satisfied	820	28%		
	Notvery satisfied	519	18%		
	Satisfied	428	14%		
	Very satisfied	92	3%		
	TOTAL	2964	100%		

The student satisfaction rate for the entire "Raw materials" dimension

Perceived quality of Raw Materials

- Overall dissatisfaction with their course (Visibility of the course : The visibility of the course is a significant indicator for both teachers and students. It provides information on the social and professional significance of the knowledge programmed, and also indicates whether or not there are links between the different parts of the programme. It is this indicator which gives meaning to the training programme and shows the interest of each module and its position within the training system, i.e. its contribution to the initial training of students.

- Overall dissatisfaction with their training programme (Clarity and layout of modules): The clarity of a module can be explained firstly by a clear definition of its objective and secondly by the implementation of effective means to achieve this objective. It can also be explained by a well thought-out distribution of modules, from the simplest to the most complex. Arranging the modules transversally and vertically is a delicate operation and requires a collegial team effort. Interdisciplinarity and decompartmentalisation of disciplines is a requirement that must be met.

The selection of modules and their diversification are unavoidable measures to guarantee the richness of training in terms of knowledge, interpersonal skills and know-how.

- Overall dissatisfaction with their course of study (quality of courses on offer) :Traditional courses of study predominate on the map of university courses on offer, despite the recommendations of recent reforms encouraging the modernisation of courses on offer. The reconfiguration of university educational architecture and the introduction of the LMD structure

have still not succeeded in creating a paradigm shift in terms of the effectiveness and quality of training.

- Overall dissatisfaction with their training programme (professionalisation of training): A new conception of the training course has been prescribed by the competent authorities in a form known as integrative alternation accompanied by a new spirit of professional socialisation. The added value of the new concept is explained by a new approach to improving the training/employment match. It involves adopting a reflective posture to maximise the relationship between theoretical foundations and teaching practices.

- Overall dissatisfaction with their training programme (Digitalisation of training) : Digitalising training means integrating digital technologies into the various training systems, whether they already exist or are in the process of being created. This is Digital Learning.

Digitising vocational training means : developing the overall training offering, improving productivity and responsiveness, offering new and interactive uses, adapting to the new uses of learners (their needs, their pace), reaching a greater number of people and providing new added value.

The digitalisation of vocational training therefore implies the use of new learning models adapted to the modes and users of today's world of work.

- Overall dissatisfaction with their course (attractiveness and employability of the course): A high level of attractiveness and employability is the key to the success of a training programme: the high number of enrolments tells us something about the perceived value of the content of each training programme. The brand image of each training programme depends on: its marketing arguments, the means of communication and dissemination of information used, the visibility of the training pathway, the competence and reputation of the trainers, its job, training and skills references and the opportunities and employability of the training.

3. Overview

The benefits of student evaluation of teachers are enormous, and touch on a number of areas of educational policy and learning :

3.1. Benefits for education policy : The evaluation of teachers by their students provides policy-makers with valuable information on the quality of teaching in educational institutions. These evaluations can be used as a basis for developing policies to improve the quality of

education, by identifying the strengths and weaknesses of teachers, curricula and teaching methods. (Ishikawa, 1986).

3.2. Benefits for the formalisation of curricula: The evaluation of teachers by students makes it possible to measure the extent to which the learning objectives defined in the curricula are being achieved. Feedback from students can help to identify gaps in the curricula and make the necessary adjustments to ensure a better match between students' expectations and the teaching objectives. (Bourdon, & Thélot, 1999).

3.3. Benefits for school projects : Student evaluations of teachers can contribute to the development of stronger school projects. By identifying successful teachers and understanding the teaching practices that contribute to their success, institutions can promote these approaches and encourage the spread of good practice among their teaching staff. (Nicol, & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006).

3.4. Benefits for the teacher's educational project : Student evaluations of teachers provide teachers with direct feedback on their teaching practices. This feedback can help them become aware of their strengths and weaknesses, identify areas for improvement and adjust their approach to better meet students' needs. (Nicol, & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006).

3.5. Benefits for the learner's project : Student evaluation of teachers enables learners to actively participate in their own educational journey. By giving their opinion on the teaching they receive, students are encouraged to think critically, express their needs and commit to their learning. This fosters their responsibility and autonomy, contributing to their personal development.

In short, the evaluation of teachers by their students has many advantages for educational policy, the formalisation of curricula, school projects, teachers' pedagogical projects and learners' projects. By using these assessments as an effective tool, educational institutions can foster a culture of quality and engage in continuous improvement of teaching and learning.

Conclusion

This study undertook an in-depth exploration of the impact of student evaluation of teaching (SEE) on improving the education and training system, with particular emphasis on its key role in promoting a quality culture within academic institutions. The results of our survey of students at Hassan II University revealed general dissatisfaction with various aspects of their educational experience, ranging from the quality of material resources to the appropriateness of the teaching

methods used. These findings clearly underline the need to systematically and rigorously integrate student feedback into continuous improvement processes.

The scientific relevance of this research can be seen at several levels. Firstly, it makes a significant contribution to improving the quality of teaching by providing a unique perspective on learners' experience. Secondly, it promotes student engagement and satisfaction by giving them a voice in the educational process. Thirdly, it enables the dynamic adaptation of study programmes to the changing needs of learners and the labour market. Fourthly, it facilitates informed decision-making based on robust empirical data. Finally, it encourages the development of a holistic quality culture in higher education.

Understood. Here's a more global and less pointed statement to convey that your hypotheses were supported by your results :

The findings of this study largely aligned with our initial hypotheses, providing valuable insights into the role of Student Evaluation of Teaching (SET) in enhancing educational quality. Our results demonstrate a consistent pattern that supports the theoretical framework underpinning this research, reinforcing the significance of student feedback in the continuous improvement of higher education institutions.

Our research opens up promising new perspectives for optimising the use of EQA as a strategic tool for promoting a quality culture in higher education. It highlights the crucial importance of active and committed student participation in the assessment process, as well as the need for judicious and methodical use of assessment results. This holistic and inclusive approach aims to create an environment conducive to continuous educational improvement and pedagogical innovation, while responding adequately to the complex and multidimensional challenges of contemporary higher education.

The scientific implications of this research are manifold. It contributes to the existing literature on Student Evaluation of Teaching (SET) by providing empirical data specific to the Moroccan context. Moreover, it paves the way for new research avenues on the interaction between student perception and higher education quality in developing countries.

Regarding future perspectives, this study raises several questions that merit further investigation. For instance, it would be relevant to explore the long-term impact of SET on teachers' careers and curriculum evolution. A comparative analysis with other Moroccan or

international universities could also provide interesting insights into the generalization of our results.

Among the limitations of this research, we can cite the focus on a single university, which may restrict the generalization of results. Additionally, a longitudinal approach could offer a more comprehensive perspective on the evolution of SET's impact over time.

The main contributions of this research lie in its enhancement of our understanding of quality improvement mechanisms in Moroccan higher education. It provides concrete data on student perceptions, thus offering decision-makers and university administrators valuable information to guide their policies and practices. Finally, this study lays the groundwork for a methodological framework for continuous evaluation of teaching quality, thereby contributing to the establishment of a culture of continuous improvement in Moroccan higher education.

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